

Analysis of Signs in Greco-Roman-Nordic Culture and Modern Use

Using EPEMC to decipher hidden origins of signs & glyphs related to the zodiacs and days

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ABSTRACT

Comparing days, months, planets, and zodiacs in GR and NT systems to look for thunderbolt and plasma-electromagnetic glyphology. Figures presented and Tables compiled give startling and unique cross-references punctuated with occasional contradictory meanings due to historical alterations. Overall cohesion remains strong, but predictions related to past behavior remain elusive and mysterious due to unforeseeable mechanistic changes to solar system arrangement. Despite this, analysis of the past does yield some intrinsically beneficial information regarding previous cataclysms, ages of mankind, and cultural anchors that generally go unchallenged in modern thought and daily use.

Keywords: Zodiac - days of the week - months- Greco-Roman - Norse - signs/glyphs

Presentation

Figure 1 - the Day's Astrology Signs

Figure 2 - The Planets' Signs credit: P. Guinard

Figure 3 - the Zodiacal Signs

Figure 4 - the Sign "Rulers"

<i>Sign</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Dates</i>	<i>Traits</i>	<i>Ruler</i>
Aries	♈	Mar. 20 – Apr. 18	Energy, initiative	Mars
Taurus	♉	Apr. 19 – May 20	Reliability, persistence	Venus
Gemini	♊	May 21 – June 20	Versatility, curiosity	Mercury
Cancer	♋	June 21 – July 22	Intuition, sympathy	Moon
Leo	♌	July 23 – Aug. 22	Confidence, self-expression	Sun
Virgo	♍	Aug. 23 – Sept. 22	Analysis, perfectionism	Mercury
Libra	♎	Sept. 23 – Oct. 22	Balance, harmony	Venus
Scorpio	♏	Oct. 23 – Nov. 21	Passion, intensity	Pluto (modern), Mars (old)
Sagittarius	♐	Nov. 22 – Dec. 21	Adventure, independence	Jupiter
Capricorn	♑	Dec. 22 – Jan. 19	Ambition, organization	Saturn
Aquarius	♒	Jan. 20 – Feb. 18	Originality, vision	Uranus (modern), Saturn (old)
Pisces	♓	Feb. 19 – Mar. 19	Sensitivity, faith	Neptune (modern), Jupiter (old)

Figure 5 - Signs with Rulers and dates

Aries		♈
Taurus		♉
Gemini		♊
Cancer		♋
Leo		♌
Virgo		♍
Libra		♎
Scorpio		♏
Sagittarius		♐
Capricorn		♑
Aquarius		♒
Pisces		♓

Figure 6 - Zodiacs correlated with common images

Discussion

For further reference, please review the following tables:

Table 1 - Comparison of Days of the Week and Greco-Roman vs. Nordic celestial references

Day (English)	Romance Language (Spanish)	Nordic Root	Celestial Body
Sunday	<i>Domingo</i>	The Sun	Sol
Monday	Lunes - Moon	The Moon	Luna
Tuesday	Martes - Mars/Ares	Tyr - God of War	Mars
Wednesday	Miercoles - Mercury/Hermes	Wodin - King of Gods Or Heimdall (1000 eyes)	Jupiter > Mercury
Thursday	Jueves - Jupiter/Zeus	Thor - God of Thunder	Mars/Jupiter (Electricity)
Friday	Viernes - Venus/Athene	Freya - Venus' first phase	Venus (originally Metis)
Saturday	Sabado - <i>Sabbath</i> /Saturn	Bor or Frigg - Saturn	Saturn

Table 2 - Months vs. Roman and Nordic Names

Month	Roman to English	Nordic Month and Meaning ¹
January	Janus or Gemini	4 Dorri - Bare Frost
February	Purity/Purification ²	5 Goa - Sowing Month
March	Mars Month	6 Einmanudur - One Month
April	Aphrodite	7 Harpa - a female spirit
May	Maia (wife of Vulcan)	8 Skerpla - another goddess
June	Juno (Hera) Month ³	9 Solmanadur - Sun Month
July	Julius' month (formerly 5th month)	10 Heyannir - Hay Collection
August	Augustus' month (formerly 6th month)	11 Tvimanidur - Two Month
September	7th Month	12 Haustmanadur - Autumn Month
October	8th Month	1 Gormanudur - Butchering Month
November	9th Month	2 Ylir - Yule Month

¹ http://freya.theladyofthelabyrinth.com/?page_id=808

² <https://www.crowl.org/Lawrence/time/months.html>

³ Hera/Juno is Saturn after the rings formed.

December	10th Month ⁴	3 Morsugur - Gut Fat Suckling Month
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Planets and Signs, Days and Months

From the above comparison, we see some excellent correlation and agreement between the Greco-Roman (GR) and the Norse/Teutonic (NT) systems from which English has inherited the days of the week. However, the months are only similar in one regard, and that is in agreement that the height of summer is owed to the sun, helios; however in the GR system Sol is Saturn, in the form of Juno. Comparing this with the Zodiacs, we see a *hypothesis* emerge that this was in the age of Leo, again, 12kya (roughly). This would correspond with other EPEMC papers.⁵

Of note also in the months is that Janus or January, the two-faced god of doors and gates, is not associated with the clear zodiacal counterpart, Gemini. This reflects (as does the erasure of NT month meanings in English history) the influence of Roman calendar re-working, as Januarius was an addition that came later.

It is obvious that it, and Februarius, were added after the Mars cataclysm because the months are so numbered to end at 10 with December. The month of destruction (Janus) and of Purification, were later re-additions when the Earth orbit re-normalized to 365.26 days.⁶ Prior to that the year was 350 days, and each month was 35 days long.⁷ It is unclear, however, why Janus was invoked, as Janus is hailing with Capricorn. This *could* reflect the changes due to layering, as evidenced by not one but two emperors of Rome changing the names of months in the time just before the modern era of Pisces.

Aries as a sign is matching with Mars (Ares) the god, with the month of Mars, and is the strongest correlation yet supplied for the signs and months comparison. This is probably reflected by the growing impetus (with improved techniques) to record the cataclysms accurately, especially upon the “betrayal” of Mars and near collision.⁸

As for the days comparison, there are numerous interesting correlations. First, starting with Tuesday (Tyr’s Day), we see that originally the planet Mars/Ares as the God of War was Tyr. The shift to favoring Thor came later as Mars was the only planet left to be seen (aside from sun and moon), and thus Thor’s increased usage with Tyr’s subsequent decline in popularity. Originally, of course, Thor was the god of thunder, and was the planet Mercury, but this was ended quickly as he became Mars and Heimdall of the 1000 eyes became Mercury, or Hermes, the attendant lord to Odin/Zeus (planet Jupiter). Meanwhile, Jupiter was favored in NT system on Wednesday (Wodin’s Day), while in Latin languages was favored as Thursday (Thor’s Day). Thus the ambiguity as to whether Thor was the planet Jupiter or Mars is increased. As the NT system is favored in English, it is especially confusing as this leaves Thursday in ambiguity, as representing the power of thunder and electromagnetism (the shared power of Thor and Odin) together.

Moving to Friday, it becomes clear that the goddess Freya refers to the early phase of Venus when Venus performed the new role of mother goddess.⁹ Remember that Venus emerged from Jupiter alone. However, prior to this, the goddess Metis and Jupiter had an “affair”, and Metis was destroyed.

⁴ <https://svmmaapologia.files.wordpress.com/2015/12/images-11.png?w=1000>

⁵ This is the fifth paper in the series, and no presuppositions were made (non-apriori). When analysis yields correlation that is striking, it is a method of testing the proposed as well as previous hypotheses.

⁶ “Worlds in Collision,” I. Velikovsky, 1950

⁷ Prior to that period, years were exactly 360 days; a point **insisted upon around the world.**

⁸ Bear in mind Mars (Houyi in China), was the last of the old gods and had “shot down” the 9 suns (of the menorah) and saved mankind from the boiling heat of Muspelheim. Therefore the prophecy that Ragnarok will commence with the death of Thor and only Baldr (?#) and Hodr (Triton) will remain in existence.

⁹ This role was not inherited from Juno/Hera/Frigg! It’s very confusing as it would have been a nice symmetry of mother-daughter themes. In most family-oriented religions this would be the way it was proposed. However, that wasn’t how the celestial bodies moved. If anything, Freya was a competition for Frigg, like a step-daughter would be.

Thor has 3 mothers: Frigg, Freya, and Gaia (Earth-mother). Frigg is Juno/Hera, and is the original mother of the gods, that is Saturn¹⁰. However she is not honored as the role of Saturn was seriously decreased by the time of both NT and GR calendrical systems. She was regarded as “jealous” of Zeus’ many rendezvous, meaning that the planet Saturn always seemed both overshadowed, and also busy attacking the “sons of Zeus” with challenges. In Norse (and Hindu) traditions this was interpreted as a war of the Aesir/Vanir sets of gods. However, in Greek tradition it was the love affairs and twisted behaviors of gods, sometimes with mortals, sometimes demigods (moons), and sometimes titans and monsters (zodiacs, as in *when* such events happened - the backdrop).

The resultant “affairs” of Jupiter in the Jovian host-star period¹¹ must have made for colorful tales. The periods of frequent warfare and cataclysms have been the most memorable (culturally) myths. Although the Mars cataclysm or “betrayal” was strong in the form of disease and pestilence, Thor quickly overcame his madness and he was forgiven [or the entire issue was blamed (again) upon the caprice of angry goddesses, such as Kali Yuga]. However the jovial¹² and yet capricious and violent (drunken like) behaviors of Zeus, King of the Gods, have become somewhat of a joke, that is never forgotten and yet a source of nervous laughter.¹³

Saturday is, meanwhile, a very straightforward analysis, easily drawing comparisons with the biblical sabbath to Saturn/Shamash. In some traditions, the Sabbath is on Sunday, which would be a more literal rendition of the meaning of Shamash. However, initially Shamash was Helios, that is to say, Saturn. In future studies, the comparison of Egyptian and Sumero-Babylonian calendrical systems from the same periods might yield interesting comparisons with the GR system.

Analysis of the Signs with EU/PEMC modeling

At first glance the sign for Sunday is uniquely Electric Universe-esque. Never would one expect Sol to produce such a symbol. Without a telescope one would never see a planet move in front of the sun, and certainly not so large (Jupiter is about a tenth that size). This is clearly related to the plasmaglyph demonstrated in PEMC paper 1 and in “On the Origins of Religions”¹⁴ (to which this paper is a companion).

The moon sign is a clear reference to moon phases and no time will be spent on it, here.

The sign for Tuesday is the sign for Ares/Mars. It is postulated herein that the symbol arising from the upper right is not an arrow but instead the final plasma streamer in glow mode, reaching out to a distant body. Perhaps the planet was in motion away from Earth, it is not known.

¹⁰ Kronus is Hera’s father, meaning the brown-dwarf star. Hera/Frigg had the rings which were beautiful. In Egypt, however Horus was the heir to Osiris, the heir of Atum-Re. Horus’ eye actually referred to Osiris. In that tradition, Osiris is saved by his wife and put back together again, indicating that the rings and moons were pulled back into orbit after Jupiter (Seth) had pulled them away. The role of the female was thus different in Egyptian record as opposed to GR and NT, reflecting probably more direct knowledge or memory; or more precise (record on stele and glyphs, rather than oral traditions which can be altered due to social biases against women.)

¹¹ As Jupiter has been decreasing in the amount of heat it releases (which exceeds what it takes in from the sun), it is unclear if the light of a Jovian “sun” was of a brown dwarf or mere reflection from young (baby) Apollo (Sol). The distance would have been much closer than the Saturnian orbit, however there was a period of severe cold, and Zeus was a fickle god. Sometimes mankind was allowed to live, and sometimes destroyed. See Enuma Elish for examples of the moods of Enlil as he played the role of Anu (the one God).

¹² From the root word jove, meaning Jupiter

¹³ In “Clash of the Titans” Zeus and Hera (and his daughter-lovers) are depicted as playing games of mankind, and yet he shows tender affections, despite delivering terribly hateful and often arbitrary punishments to all but his own sons. In “Hercules” (by Disney), the god-king is depicted as a son-loving, knee-slapping giant who loves his son and yet is nearly too foolish to notice the betrayals around him. This is a modern take on the earlier Disney depiction in “Fantasia” of a party-ending Zeus who chooses Bacchus upon whom to play a frighteningly violent joke, almost at random, as if hunting *his own children*. This multifaceted portrayal reflects mankind’s complex relationship with the god of Wednesday. Likewise Odin is similarly depicted as occasionally wise and magnanimous, a teacher-father to Thor. At other times, capricious and cruel, self-centered and narcissistic; as one might portray a drunk father with a gambling issue (a common trope). For examples of this see “Thor” and “Thor: Dark-World” for comparisons of contemporary depictions.

¹⁴ Both of these can be found by accessing “On the Origins of Religions,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2018

The sign for Wednesday is the most complicated and tells, therefore, a complicated story. In Gr the sign belongs to Hermes/Mercury and would refer, therefore to Heimdall. However, from the NT the sign would belong to Jupiter, so which is correct?

The lowest symbol, the “celtic cross” is a sign signifying the polar conjunction, that is the age of Saturn as our Sun. The one above it then signifies the power of the Sun, and the final crescent above that is an archetype symbol for Atum-Re/Shamash/Saturn as the sun. From this depiction we can see that the symbol represents the passage of power from Bor to Wodin/Odin and possibly to Thor (from Re to Osiris to Horus). It is not merely a symbol for the day but for the spiritual alignment of the crown through root, signifying kingship and the Atman/Brahmic experience itself, as perceived in the lines of succession in kings.

The day Thursday receives the lower right celtic cross, and the upper left crescent. This is a complicated glyph. Based up the association with Jupiter it is tempting to surmise that the glyph is associating Jupiter as outside the polar conjunction, meaning the *first time Jupiter appeared* to mankind (the failure of the colinear configuration). However, it could easily be a stylized representation of a thunderbolt in storm.

Friday, belonging to Venus is also depicting the configuration. The cross has come to mean either Heaven or Earth. Venus is leaving the configuration, and this is signifying the separation of Heaven and Earth recorded worldwide, from the Chinese to the Epic of Gilgamesh to the New World.

Saturday shows clearly the cross of the Lord, which is borrowed as a symbol from the “celtic cross”, that is the polar configuration. To crucify people, was to offer them to the Lord, using just such a cross. The movement shown, however is not of a cross but of Saturnian movement away into the distance, receding. This means the end of an era, and the “resting” (Odin-sleep, or Sabbath) of the One God, until He rises again.

Analysis of the zodiacs is generally beyond this paper and would require complex star chart and constellation analysis. As complex as the changing solar system has been (complicated as well by the month altering and politics of ancient Rome), the zodiacs date back to the Atlantean and Tepe periods. Also, they vary with the cultures and with Sino-Vedic counterparts, to such a significant degree that complete decryption may prove wearisome and tediously pedantic, even arbitrary. Sometimes, themes would emerge to replace concrete ideas, making the translations cumbersome.

Of the remaining planet signs, we have a trident for Neptune, which is in accord with Enki (lord of waters), former god of the sky (Ea), the first planet “Head” of Saturn, who was god before Kronus (Anu). However, the change in this precedes the GR and NT, so is not usually reflected. Here, it is. This shows that the power of the thunderbolt indeed is passed father to son and can be extrapolated to extend backwards to the ancient forefather.

The sign for Uranus may or may not refer to a cataclysm whereby the sign for Gemini signifies when or why (two faced planetoid?) something collided with the young god and he became “suspended in the river Styx” (hung from the heels) and then lord of the underworld. The planet is, itself, quite odd enough without the references to being associated with death. Its extreme tilt is what gives the appearance of destruction.

The sign for Aries is a ram, and is associated with Ares, however this is incorrect memory. Before that, they were associated with Saturn. The movement from father to son (sun).

Taurus is associated with the Bull of Heaven, that is the age of Jupiter. The bull is also associated with Hercules/Heraclides, whom is named after Hera though his mother is mortal, and father is Zeus-Jupiter.

Gemini is associated most likely with the toroid formation in plasmaglyphology.

Cancer is associated with the Venus/Mars conjunction and “mating” period of discharge, during the Jovian era.

Libra is a balance sign, and is associated with the Venus/Mother. The sign glyph is of a rising sun, signifying the “Morning Star.”¹⁵

¹⁵ Or “evening star”

Virgo and Scorpio are associated with the thunderbolts and plasma “rain” of comet tails. The scorpio glyph in particular is associated with male sexual potency, as related to thunderbolt energy, and may refer also to “warrior madness”. The signs it rules share similar origins and indicate either failing conjunctions, or more likely the authority of passing male leadership. Bear in mind that Mercury was Thor, but then became Heimdall, while Mars became the *hot* version of Mercury, Thor.

While Aquarius is obviously a waves glyph, Sagittarius is unclear.

Capricorn appears to be associated with a goat sign, which may refer again to a separate plasma streamer from Mars, as opposed to Venus. It is also associated with Saturn, and may reference the wandering movements of Odin upon Sleipnir, (or Atum-Re, leaving our immediate Heavens).

Pisces is a clear birkeland current phenomenon seen in many plasma glyphs, called a Bennett (or Z) pinch. The sign is associated with the Religious Period, post Messiah, and yet descends after ages of warfare. Its associated glyph of a crescent above the Earth clearly refers to the age of one sun (Sol), the “light”. This is the present ending zodiacal age. If there was an Atlantean Period astronomical tradition that was handed down in (first cave cults, then death cults, then wizardry, now science) traditions all over, it would point to a belief in transition from the current arrangement to a new one (Aquarius). Given the current drop in magnetosphere protection, perhaps the irony is that more cosmic rays and EMF waves will reach Earth than ever before in recorded human history.

NOTE - Pluto is a modern sign invention. The glyph has no immediate ancient analysis value. To force one would certainly be a reference to Nibiru (planet X), a “dark star” (another theme for another paper) which has been postulated to exist based upon gravitational efforts. It is associated with the age of Scorpio. The sign of Scorpio is not helpful in determining the nature of a **real** tenth planet in the cycles of cosmic destruction. The Chinese have insisted there have been “ten suns”, however this one would not reflect and would be on a highly elliptical orbit. Scorpio is associated with a time in approximately 3500-4500 years from now. The answer to this riddle may [hopefully] not appear anytime soon.

Conclusion

The signs for glyphs of months, planets, zodiacs, and days are all cross-correlated records of age changes. The original zodiacs may be contained on the stele of Gobekli Tepe, more research is needed. The original month and day names from Egyptian and Sumerian-Babylonian records also need EPEMC analysis. This paper dealt with the two most recent currents of influence to the English day and month systems, the Greco-Roman and the Norse-Teutonic systems.

The signs and days and month names cross-correlate in interesting ways, which combined with the ages and glyphs may provide past summary and future insight. Ambiguities due to the nature of changing calendars and bureaucratic involvement and intrusion will inevitably make precise conclusions difficult to impossible. Where cross-correlations are clear, firm evidence to support a radically “alien sky” [4] to our own present sky appear. This supports previously present biological and archaeological and geological evidence.

The implications are rudimentary, but profound. History forgotten is identity lost, and a deeper study of these may yield insights into human psychology, behavior, and cultural disease as well as provide healthy solutions.

References

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4. “Symbols of an Alien Sky,” D Talbott, youtube.com, “Project Thunderbolts”, thunderbolts.info